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Physical Classroom Layout and Teachers' Teaching Behaviour as Correlates of Students' Satisfaction in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated physical classroom layout and teachers' teaching behaviour as correlates of students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state. Two research questions and two hypotheses were answered and tested in the study. The design employed for the study was correlation design. The population of the study was 71,960 public senior secondary students in Rivers State out of which 418 students were drawn as sample for the study using multi stage sampling technique consisting of random and stratified sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a 30-item questionnaire named "Classroom Climate Questionnaire" (CCQ), a 30-item questionnaire titled "Instructional Quality Questionnaire" (IQQ) and a 20-item questionnaire tagged "Student Satisfaction Questionnaire" (SSQ). The reliability of the instruments was estimated using Cronbach alpha statistic and produced coefficients of 0.84, 0.93 and 0.87 for the three instruments. There were 418 copies of questionnaire which were administered but 403 copies which represented 96.4% were successfully retrieved and used for the data analysis. The research questions raised were answered using both simple and multiple regression analysis while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test associated with simple regression and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The result of the study indicated that teachers' teaching behaviour, competitive classroom environment, effective classroom management and cognitive activation all had high effect on students' satisfaction while physical classroom layout and supportive teacher had low effects. The study concluded that based on the findings of the study that a low but positive relationship between physical classroom layout and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It was recommended among others that there is need for the government to give adequate attention to physical facilities and layout planning in public secondary schools.

Keywords: Physical facilities, teaching behaviour, students' satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential social service provided for citizens across different levels and types for both personal and national growth and development. The relevance of education to society cannot be ignored. In developing nations, industrialization, transformation, and development remains mere wishes except the benefits of education are leveraged upon. Similarly, for individuals, institutions and nations to excel in this cutthroat world, citizens need to be properly educated in line with the needs of the society. This is because, in any society, citizens who are well informed with the right skill sets, knowledge and values are those who can apply better solutions to the problems of the society and are the foundation of growth and development in the society.

Generally, and in most countries of the world, there are three fundamental categories of education that exists. There are two main types of education which are mostly practiced because of how

organized they are and their contribution to the society. The first is formal, which starts in elementary school and goes up to a tertiary level of education. It includes teaching students' intellectual skills, enhancing their knowledge and improving on their attitude. Establishing the guidelines and procedures necessary to complete the formal degree is made possible in this form of education. On the other hand, there is also an informal learning which is done without the use of special equipment. It is believed that by simply reading books, repeating practical activities, an individual will get an informal education that will balance an equal skill in everyday life. The third kind of education is non-formal, and it involves knowledge of initiatives like adult literacy and basic education programmes that support the educational system. There isn't a schedule, curriculum, or upper age limit that allows for greater flexibility in this kind of education. The system of education is therefore determined by convenience according to the desire and arrangement of the teacher and the learner. However, the formal form of education is the system that is globally practiced due to its relevance in solving societal problems and contributing to individual and societal growth and development.

It is well acknowledged that one of the most important success factors in fostering economic growth and development in any country whether developed or developing and even around the world is education. Additionally, it is thought that education can spur economic growth and progress in any nation, but especially in developing nations that are striving to catch up with others. It is unclear exactly what amount of education is necessary for the necessary development in a nation that is regarded as developing, and there is no clear way to correlate educational attainment with developmental outcomes. There is a belief that education across all levels somehow guarantees the availability of labour for the advancement of the country. It is maintained that a sophisticated and educated populace has necessitated and placed labour in the appropriate sectors to contribute their fair share to economic growth and development in the country and as such, no level of education can be ignored for the other as they all interrelate to contribute to developmental outcomes in the long run.

Citizens gain knowledge and skills from the type of education provided by the society especially when it is formal, and it also helps them develop their personalities as well as maximize the opportunities available to the society. However, despite all of these facts, the literacy rate in Nigeria still stands at 77.62% (Fakiya, 2023) which is one of the least in Africa with an unemployment rate of 40.6% and all of these call for decisive actions that will transform the education system for the benefit of all. It is only citizens who have a sense of patriotism and national identity that can advance their society and this is only based on the quality of education that they have received. Nation building is only possible when the citizens have a sense of national belonging, and this is cultivated through the type of education that is provided for the members of the society. Similarly, the success in life of an individual is greatly influenced by their education and it is only those who make a meaning out of their own life that can contribute to the advancement of their society. Education has a significant effect on people's chances to maintain their quality of life and by implication that of the society. Educational scholars agree that education is the cornerstone of a society that leads to economic prosperity, social prosperity, and political stability and as such cannot be ignored in the process of nation building. The type and level of education a person has influences their social and economic standing because it increases their capacity to control their quality of life. It can aid an individual in avoiding poverty and fostering social harmony and democracy and this has implications on the prosperity of the society as a whole. It is based on this understanding that different stakeholders invest in the education sector.

Statement of the Problem

The need for raising high performing students has been top priority of several educational stakeholders and several research have been carried out to find out how different educational resources can help improve the performance of students and enhanced quality of education across different levels of education. However, despite the quality and quantity of educational resources provided for students especially at the secondary education level, very little success is recorded. This may be evidenced in the lack of adequate students' satisfaction. Achieving students' satisfaction is essential to making them learn and how this can be realized needs to be given top priority. It is against this backdrop that the researcher investigated physical classroom layout and teachers' teaching behaviour as correlates of students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers state.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study investigated physical classroom layout and teachers' teaching behaviour as correlates of students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. determine the extent to which physical classroom layout contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. examine the extent to which teachers' teaching behaviour contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the extent to which physical classroom layout contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the extent to which teachers' teaching behaviour contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance;

1. Physical classroom layout does not significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Teachers' teaching behaviour does not significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Physical Classroom Layout and Students' Satisfaction in Secondary Schools

Physical learning environment and its layout no doubt play important roles in the education system across all levels of education but instead of physical environments, over the years, the social and psychological settings of the environment have frequently been the focus of learning environment discuss and this has undermined the importance of a suitable physical environment for learning activities in schools. According to Ene-Obong, Ibeanu, Onuoha, and Ejekwu (2012), a school's physical environment consists of its buildings, furniture, technology, instructional materials, labs, libraries, and playgrounds. All of these resources are important components of the school system that cannot be ignored if meaningful teaching and learning will take place in the school. Along with these elements, the physical environment also consists of play areas, swimming pools, and decorative items. All of these interact to determine the quality of education that can be provided to learners. The term physical environment generally refers to the actual site, structures, furnishings, infrastructure, room, and tools needed for efficient teaching and learning. However, how all of these resources interact in the learning process are very important to the education system as the availability of these resources alone does not guarantee quality education or student satisfaction from the school system.

Educational scholars have continued to investigate how relevant the physical learning environment is for the attainment of educational goals and objectives. The significance of the physical environment to academic success has been investigated by several researchers by describing the connections between classroom circumstances and learning that have been established to be relevant to the educational expectations of students and other educational stakeholders. Some researchers have shown that improved learning environments often result in higher test scores and more optimistic student attitudes, supporting the idea that the classroom environment has a significant impact on concentration levels, listening, and writing. This implies that the relevance of the school's physical environment to the different aspects of learning cannot be overemphasized. The physical layout of the classroom has psychological, physical, moral and even emotional effects on the learner and as such must be given adequate attention in the process of school administration.

The physical environments in which students learn have an impact on various aspects of their learning such as the levels of achievement in subjects like vocabulary, reading comprehension, language, the arts, mathematics, and science (Tanner, 2009). The physical layout of the school significantly affects all aspects of the learner's development and as such cannot be ignored. Students develop various skills and competencies from interacting with several types of educational resources in the physical classroom environment and the way these resources are arranged for learners determines the speed and quality of educational objectives that will be achieved.

Teachers' Teaching Behaviour and Students' Satisfaction in Secondary Schools

There are several attitudes that teachers exhibit in the process of teaching for which they are known and students in most cases believe that this forms part of the teacher's behaviour. These are practicing that the teacher will always exhibit in the course of teaching by which the teacher is known and addressed and while some of these expressions are appreciated by the students in the learning process, others may be disturbing to the learner. Asif, Fakhra, Tahir, and Shabbir (2016) in one of their studies found out that average school test scores for some teachers differ widely which indicates that there are some degree of grouping of teachers in schools based on their teaching behaviour. In comparison to high scoring educational institutions, low scoring learning institutions employ more new teachers and have a smaller pool of experienced teachers who may not have formed the required professional teaching behaviour required to achieve targeted educational goals and objectives and enhance students learning satisfaction. The low experience teachers in low-scoring schools may be reflected in the fact that these teachers there hold degrees and experiences that limits their ability to deliver quality teaching services. It is therefore common to see students with low learning satisfaction being taught by teachers who lacked the required teaching behaviour needed to drive enhanced educational performance among students.

One of the factors that has hindered efficient teaching and learning in schools is poor behaviour among staff and students. The teaching and learning process during across all levels of education can be severely hampered by unruly classroom behavior (Medina & Reverte, 2019) which could be perpetrated by either staff or students. These behaviors may also have an adverse effect on students' perceptions of their school's quality, their relationships with teachers, and even their likelihood of succeeding academically (Baos et al., 2017) as well as the interaction of students among one another. When the behaviour of the teacher during instructional delivery is not appealing, it can result to a toxic classroom climate which can affect the quality of instruction as well as students' satisfaction from learning. This explains why teachers in most schools are guided by professional ethics which are geared towards making the teacher well-behaved and contributing to students' satisfaction and success in school.

METHODOLOGY

The design employed for the study was correlation design. The population of the study was 71,960 public senior secondary students in Rivers State out of which 418 students were drawn as sample for the study using multi stage sampling technique consisting of random and stratified sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a 30-item questionnaire named "Classroom Climate Questionnaire" (CCQ), a 30-item questionnaire titled "Instructional Quality Questionnaire" (IQQ) and a 20-item questionnaire tagged "Student Satisfaction Questionnaire" (SSQ). The reliability of the instruments was estimated using Cronbach alpha statistic and produced coefficients of 0.84, 0.93 and 0.87 for the three instruments. The research questions raised were answered using both simple and multiple regression analysis while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test associated with simple regression and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What is the extent to which physical classroom layout contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple regression analysis on the extent to which physical classroom layout contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remark
1	.321 ^a	.103	-.196	4.04832	Low and Positive Relationship

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physical_Classroom_Layout

Table 1 indicated that with an r value of 0.321, there existed a low but positive relationship between physical classroom layout and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In the same manner, the value of r^2 of 0.103 implied that 10.3% of students' satisfaction is accounted for by the physical classroom layout while the remaining 89.7% is accounted for by other factors outside the physical classroom layout. This means that physical classroom layout has a minimal effect on students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *What is the extent to which teachers' teaching behaviour contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple regression analysis on the extent to which teachers' teaching behaviour contributes to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remark
1	.917 ^a	.841	.788	1.70546	Very High and Positive Relationship

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers_Teaching_Behaviour

Table 2 showed that with an r value of 0.917, there existed a very high and positive relationship between teachers' teaching behaviour and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Furthermore, the value of r^2 of 0.841 implied that 84.1% of students' satisfaction is accounted for by the teachers' teaching behaviour while the remaining 15.9% is accounted for by other indicators outside the teachers' teaching behaviour. This means that the teachers' teaching behaviour has a great effect on students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Physical classroom layout does not significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: t-test Associated with Simple Regression Analysis that physical classroom layout does not significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Decision
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-6.000	79.845		-.075	.945	Retain Hypothesis
	Physical_Classroom_Layout	2.167	3.696	.321	.586	.599	

a. Dependent Variable: Students_Satisfaction

Table 3 showed that with a t-value of 0.586 which is less than the critical value of 1.96 as well as a significance value of 0.599 which is more than the p-value of 0.05, the decision will be to retain the null hypothesis and this implied that physical classroom layout does not significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: Teachers’ teaching behaviour does not significantly contribute to students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression Analysis that teachers’ teaching behaviour does not significantly contribute to students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	11.419	7.421		1.539	.221	Reject Hypothesis
Teachers_Teaching_Behaviour	1.113	.280	.917	3.980	.028	

a. Dependent Variable: Students_Satisfaction

Table 4 indicated that with a t-value of 3.980 which is more than the critical value of 1.96 as well as a significance value of 0.028 which is less than the p-value of 0.05, the decision will be to reject the null hypothesis and this implied that teachers’ teaching behaviour does significantly contribute to students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Physical Classroom Layout and Students’ Satisfaction

The result of the data collected from the respondents and analyzed was able to show that there existed a low but positive relationship between physical classroom layout and students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and that 10.3% of students’ satisfaction is attributed to the physical classroom layout. Similarly, the study showed that physical classroom layout does not significantly contribute to students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This aligns with the outcome of the study by Azemati and Pourbagher (2018) which showed that flexibility and spatial dimensions, readability and accessibility, aesthetics of the space, environmental comfort, and territory and human participation are the five main factors that influence satisfaction. Attention must therefore be paid to these for the layout of the school to make sense to the students. This means that the study showed that the way the classroom environment is laid, although has a positive effect on students’ satisfaction, the magnitude of the contribution is very minimal. This implies that there are other likely factors that may account more for the satisfaction of students in these schools than the layout of the classroom and the teachers and schools in general must give attention to these needs or expectations.

Teachers’ Teaching Behaviour and Students’ Satisfaction

The result of the study showed that there existed a very high and positive relationship between teachers’ teaching behaviour and students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State while 84.1% of students’ satisfaction is determined by the teachers’ teaching behaviour. This result agrees with that of Sunitha (2021) which indicated that students were generally satisfied with the pedagogy used in the classroom and are pleased with the way teachers perform in it. The only students who are not regular attendees are those who are unaware of the teaching methodology and are therefore rarely satisfied with the pedagogy used. In a related manner, findings of the study indicated that teachers’ teaching behaviour does not significantly contribute to students’ satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This finding varies from that of Wagbara and Nwadike (2023) as well as that of Opatha (2020) which indicated that the relationship between lecturers' competence and students' satisfaction with lecturing was significantly and fully mediated, per the statistical findings of the mediation analysis. This finding suggests that the students are more

concerned about the teaching behaviour of the teacher which has a direct link on their academic performance.

Summary of Findings

1. There existed a low but positive relationship between physical classroom layout and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and 10.3% of students' satisfaction is accounted for by the physical classroom layout.
2. The study showed that there existed a very high and positive relationship between teachers' teaching behaviour and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State while 84.1% of students' satisfaction is accounted for by the teachers' teaching behaviour.
3. The study showed that physical classroom layout does not significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. Findings of the study indicated that teachers' teaching behaviour does significantly contribute to students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that a low but positive relationship between physical classroom layout and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and 10.3% of students' satisfaction is accounted for by the physical classroom layout. while a very high and positive relationship between teachers' teaching behaviour and students' satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State while 84.1% of students' satisfaction is accounted for by the teachers' teaching behaviour.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made in line with the findings of the study:

1. There is need for the government to give adequate attention to physical facilities and layout planning in public secondary schools. This means that the facilities provided in these schools should meet the need and expectation of users. The physical layout of the school should be healthy enough to address the need of students and improve on their satisfaction and performance in the school.
2. Teachers in public secondary schools need to be exposed to regular capacity building programmes such as conferences, seminars and workshops where they will acquire contemporary skills and knowledge that will enable them delivery quality teaching that will meet the need of students and objectives of the education system at the same time in an ever-dynamic school system.

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